

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VIDES****FIRST NAME: IRMA****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%.

The author used the following software: Microsoft® Word 2019 on Windows 11.

List of key concepts in this response paper:

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 8-11).
2. Plagiarism avoidance (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).
3. Style guides (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40).
4. Linguistic variants (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-26).
5. Logical flow of arguments (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11).

ACADEMIC WRITING FRAMEWORK

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is the spinal column of academia; it constitutes the main support for reinforcing new knowledge in the world, demanding precision, structure, and ethical principles. This responsibility obliges every reputable author to learn to construct one, but *how is it done?* This essay engages five primary themes to create and develop a correct academic paper: essay writing, plagiarism avoidance, style guides, linguistic variants, and logical flow of arguments, incorporating practices of Turabian style, based on the ACA-401 Coursepack by Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma.

2) ESSAY WRITING

An essential point of academic writing is to build essays with a logical construction. Personally, the most challenging part is: the beginning. Finding the right state of mind to start an essay may be an internal battle, even if the ideas are already sorted as an initial plan.

Thereafter, composing essays generally consists of three main parts: introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction sets the stage for the essay by giving context, a thesis statement, and a roadmap of what the essay will contain. The body expands the thesis more thoroughly, organized into paragraphs around concepts, with support from evidence. Lastly, the conclusion synthesizes the argument, restating the thesis without introducing new information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10).

Likewise, the writing process is important within its stages: research, planning, drafting, and editing. Cleenewerck and Gulma emphasize the importance of a focused start in this writing process, analyzing the essay question (also called thesis), investigating it, and organizing ideas into a well-thought plan. When the author develops a draft, it means transforming the plan into cohesive paragraphs. After this step, the editing will polish the essay to improve clarity and consistency (2024, 8-11). This organized approach guarantees logical consistency and adherence to academic rigor.

3) PLAGIARISM AVOIDANCE

Plagiarism is one of the most serious offenses in academia, undermining the authors' integrity, even if the content of the academic papers is correct. The Coursepack defines plagiarism as using another's ideas or words without proper acknowledgment. Examples include failing to cite direct quotations, paraphrases, statistics, or visuals sourced from others (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).

To avoid plagiarism, the Coursepack recommends diligent citation practices: As researchers, we must get the facts right, which involves providing the right sources of these facts (Turabian 2018, 139). One interesting point is about sources consulted online; sources evolve, too, as time passes; however, we must include many of the same elements as if we cite physical sources. This is why I disagree with a couple of arguments shown in the video titled "Sample RP Review Video" authored by Gulma (2018), referring to online authors and citations:

- One of the provided examples of corrections points to "EssayJack" as the document's author of the corrected paper (8:04). However, the video itself shows that "EssayJack by Wize" is a platform created by Wizedemy, Inc., being the latter the publisher, not "EssayJack."
- In addition, another example will allow me to elaborate on secondary sources vs primary ones. The video shows Isabel Allende as the author of the online article with the cited quotations (10:34); however, Goodreads is a website that recommends books. The quotes of authors such as Isabel Allende are added by the Goodreads community and are not verified by the website (Goodreads, Inc. 2022), as Wikipedia does. Therefore, it is possible that the cited quotes are not even from Allende.

Finally, Cleenewerck and Gulma underscore the need to paraphrase effectively, transforming source material into the authors' without altering a few phrases. Accurate

paraphrasing, coupled with correct citations, ensures both originality and ethical adherence.

4) STYLE GUIDES

Even though there are various styles for writing academic papers, I will center the attention of this essay on the Turabian style, which is, as highlighted in the Coursepack, a simplified version of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) tailored specifically for students and researchers. Named by its original author, Kate L. Turabian, the guide provides the principles of the CMS but has been adapted to suit the needs of academic papers, theses, and dissertations. It focuses on clarity and consistency, offering formats for citations, bibliographies, and notes that meet scholarly expectations. Turabian's method provides valuable tips for framing arguments, structuring paragraphs, and ensuring logical flow throughout an academic document (Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2024, 40).

The Coursepack underscores the versatility of this style, which accommodates both Notes-Bibliography and Author-Date citation systems. Turabian (2018, 142) explains that while the Notes-Bibliography style is ideal for humanities, emphasizing footnotes and comprehensive bibliographies, the Author-Date system suits the social and natural sciences, prioritizing parenthetical citations and reference lists. Since I am inclined toward natural sciences, this will be my citation system from now on so I can ensure consistency in citations and overall presentation.

5) LINGUISTIC VARIANTS

The way to approach linguistically a topic in academic writing is also important. To cover this topic, the Coursepack also explains the differences between American and British English. For example, American English typically uses “color” and “center,” while British English employs “colour” and “centre.” Similarly, punctuation rules vary, such as the placement of commas and periods relative to quotation marks (Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2024, 24–26). It is essential for authors who do not have English as their first language, such as myself, to understand these distinctions because adapting to the expectations of diverse academic audiences is crucial. Using the right variant and maintaining consistency enables an author, for instance, to improve the credibility and reachability of their writing.

6) LOGICAL FLOW OF ARGUMENTS

Another interesting point to understand in academic writing is the importance of logical flow, achieved through transitions and structured argumentation. Writers are encouraged to use connectors such as “however,” “one the one hand,” and “nevertheless” to guide readers through their arguments. Additionally, headings and subheadings help organize longer papers, while careful paragraphing ensures clarity.

The Coursepack advises revisiting drafts after a break to identify logical gaps and improve coherence. Keeping in mind that others will read the text will give another perspective, helping the author make proper edits. This iterative process not only strengthens arguments but also enhances the overall readability of the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11).

7) CONCLUSION

Even though the initial steps to write academically may seem scary, once the process starts with proper guidelines such as those provided in the ACA-401 Coursepack, the construction becomes more manageable, as it emphasizes structure, ethical practices, and stylistic precision. By following Turabian guidelines, for example, we students can produce polished, professional work that meets academic standards. Moreover, by adhering to the Coursepack principles, writers can produce compelling, credible, and ethically sound essays. As academic writing remains integral to scholarly pursuits, the lessons within this Coursepack offer a solid foundation for students and professionals.

REFERENCES

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- Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by: Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. Ninth Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, Adobe Digital Editions PDF.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.